

Elite Healers Sports Massage is more than just a massage, it's therapy. Visit the Elite Healers Sports Massage website at <https://www.elitehealersportsmassage.com> to book an appointment or to see their hours of operation. They are setting a higher standard in the world of massage therapy. They are a Sports Massage and Medical Massage company in New York City and their clinic is in midtown Manhattan (a.k.a. midtown in New York City). They are not a spa, but are closer to a physical therapy clinic in the sense that they are more treatment focused, than relaxation focused. Elite Healers Sports Massage services include: Sports Massage Therapy, Medical Massage Therapy, Deep Tissue Massage Therapy, Swedish Massage Therapy, Thai Massage, and Chair Massage Office Events. They provide recovery for athletes of all levels with Sports Massage. They also help people manage chronic muscle pain, recover from injuries, recover from surgery and help to provide muscle relief to those who just have regular muscle aches and pains by providing medical massage services as well. You can book a 60, 90, or 120 minute session.

Now that you know more about Elite Healers Sports Massage, let's talk about the benefits of sports massage. Whether you're a seasoned athlete looking to improve your performance or a regular jogger, sports massage can help keep you feeling your best.

Sports massage can help increase blood flow, reduce pain, ease muscle tension and improve your range of motion. It can also help prevent injuries.

Increased Blood Flow:

Sports massages improve blood flow to the muscles, bringing oxygen and nutrients to the muscle tissue. They also help remove waste products from the muscle to reduce pain and stiffness. Research shows that athletes who receive regular massages have better energy levels, improved performance and a more positive experience during a match or competition. This is because massage helps turn off the sympathetic nervous system (fight & flight), which causes a resting response in the body, reducing heart rate and blood pressure.

This also translates into less time needed to recover between training sessions or competitions. In addition, massage increases flexibility by breaking down adhesions that [Best Massage in NYC](#) form within the muscles. This can help keep the muscles in a more flexible position, which is especially helpful for those who are involved in rigorous sports.

Reduced Pain:

Sports massage is effective at decreasing pain in both athletes and non-athletes. It is used to help reduce pain and fatigue during and after intense exercise and promote recovery and flexibility. The touch of a massage interferes with the pain impulses that run towards the spinal cord and up to the brain by sending other signals along the same nerves. It also stimulates the body's natural pain killers. During exercise, muscle soreness can occur due to the metabolic insufficiency of the muscles' blood supply, which can lead to the formation of lactic acid and inflammation. A sports massage helps to flush out these waste products.

A study by Dr Anamaria Fleig Mayer at NUREAB suggests that a massage application to the quadriceps muscle can reduce pain intensity after an activity such as a run. It is unclear whether the effect was greater in athletes than non-athletes, but this study supports previous studies that suggest that massage therapy is a helpful approach to the reduction of pain.

Increased Flexibility:

Massage can increase flexibility by loosening muscles and increasing elasticity, allowing muscles to relax and stretch. Tight and inflexible muscles limit movement and cause pain. Research suggests that sports massage can increase muscle elasticity and improve range of motion in muscles. This is especially beneficial for athletes who are training for sports and need increased flexibility to perform at their best.

Injured muscles can also benefit from a massage to reduce pain and restore elasticity to the muscle. This will allow a person to maintain their range of movement during the recovery process and help them avoid further injury. While massage can provide temporary relief to injured muscles, stretching can be more effective at reducing pain and improving flexibility in the long term. However, this is a difficult task to undertake on your own and you will need to persevere with stretching and regular exercise to see long-term benefits in your body.

Reduced Stress:

Having a massage is a great way to reduce stress. This is because massage increases the level of positive hormones in a person's brain, such as endorphins. This makes a person feel more relaxed and calmer, which is also beneficial for them to be able to cope with pain. This is because pain triggers a response in the body which releases a stress hormone called cortisol.

When the level of cortisol is high, it can increase pain levels even more. This is why sports massage helps to reduce pain by reducing mental and physical stress.

Athletes often seek out sports massage before a sporting event or intense training session to help prepare their muscles and keep them supple. This can help prevent injury and improve performance. Now that you know more about the benefits of sports massage, it is time to go back to the website of Elite Healers Sports Massage out of New York City to book an appointment today. Their professional staff are awaiting your call and are ready to help you today!